

READING COMPREHENSION AND THE SPECIAL STRATEGIES TO ENHANCE IT

Urolov Eshmamat Nurmamatovich

The second year Master of Foreign Language and Literature

Denau Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedogogy

eshmamaturolov1996@gmail.com

Abstract: *According to some researchers around the world, reading skills play a significant part in the development of our world outlook. That is why, we should develop these skills very well in order to gain sufficient knowledge that we need for variety of reasons in our education process. So comprehension is something which is a vital part of reading. While we are reading, we should do our best to understand and get the gist of what we are reading for better overall awareness. Through learning and using reading strategies and modifying the way we read, it is possible to develop our reading comprehension skills and making what we read more straightforward as well as more interesting. This article will explore what reading comprehension is and provides with the most useful strategies that can be used to improve our reading skills.*

Keywords: *Reading comprehension, vocabulary build-up, the context clues, noting down a summary.*

Аннотация: *По мнению некоторых исследователей, значительную роль в развитии нашего мировоззрения играют навыки чтения. Это главная причина того, что мы должны усердно способствовать развитию этих навыков, чтобы получить знания, необходимые в образовательных целях. Таким образом, понимание текста - это то, что является жизненно важной частью чтения. При чтении, необходимо делать все возможное, чтобы понять суть того, что мы читаем, для лучшей общей осведомленности. Изучая и используя стратегии чтения и изменяя то, как мы читаем, можно развить наши навыки понимания прочитанного и сделать то, что мы читаем, более простым и интересным. В этой статье будет рассмотрено, что такое понимание прочитанного, и представлены наиболее полезные стратегии, которые можно использовать для улучшения наших навыков чтения.*

Ключевые слова: *понимание прочитанного, наращивание словарного запаса, контекстные подсказки, запись резюме.*

Annotatsiya: *Dunyodagi bazi tadqiqotchilarning fikriga ko'ra, o'qish ko'nikmalari dunyo qarashimizning rivojlanishida katta muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shuning uchun ham, biz ta'lim jarayonida turli sabablarga ko'ra biz uchun zarur bo'lgan yetarli bilimga ega bo'lish uchun ushbu ko'nikmalarni juda yaxshi rivojlantirishimiz zarur. Demak, tushunish o'qishning muhim bir qismi hisoblanadi. Biz o'qiyotgan paytimizda, umumiy xabardorlikni oshirish uchun o'qiyotgan narsamizni tushunish va mohiyatini bilib olish uchun imkon qadar harakat qilishimiz kerak. O'qish va o'qish strategiyalarini qo'llash va o'qish uslubimizni o'zgartirish orqali o'qib tushunish ko'nikmalarimizni rivojlantirish va o'qigan narsamizni yanada sodda va qiziqarli qilishimiz mumkin.*

Ushbu maqola o'qib tushunish ko'nikmasi nima ekanligini o'rganadi va o'qish ko'nikmalarimizni yaxshilash uchun qo'llanilishi mumkin bo'lgan eng foydali strategiyalar bilan taminlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: *O'qib tushunish, so'z boyligini shakllantirish, kontekstga doir ma'lumotlar, qisqacha xulosa yozish.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, everything is changing at an alarmingly fast that we strive to keep up with these changes. In addition to this, the notion of globalization has become commonplace and it is influencing on the whole globe. It is natural that during this kind of situation when there is a huge demand for more productive study of all walks of life, this demand which has also an impact on our country and the way the English is taught is not neglected. Consequently, variety of up-to-date technologies and programs have come into use and they are being put into practice so as to teach English to students more effectively and in a more enjoyable way. Simultaneously, as the Internet and the ICTs are being developed, learning as well as teaching foreign languages and enhancing the reading comprehension in a foreign language makes teachers take on numerous responsibilities. Setting up a communication and a co-operation with the world is one of the most important ways which are useful for economic as well as social development of a certain country. English is a tool that influences on the globalization process. For this reason, English has been given a special attention in recent years to promote it. Uzbekistan is also no exception in this process, including the decision of the Cabinet of Minister of the Republic Uzbekistan dated 19.01.2022 № 34 "On Additional Measures to improve The Study of Foreign Languages" defining the demand for the study of the English language will present.

Four skills are taken into consideration in the process of teaching English and we usually divide these skills into two groups: receptive and productive skills. Listening and reading skills are receptive skills; speaking and writing skills constitute the

productive skills. We usually tend to believe that speaking and listening skills are a matter of the utmost importance while teaching children English but we should not undervalue the reading comprehension as it serves as a foundation in the process of gaining knowledge. As Mary Schmich once said, "Reading is a discount ticket to everywhere." So, only through mastering our reading comprehension, we can develop the other skills above mentioned.

Reading comprehension and its advantages

Being able to understand or realize what you are reading is considered to be reading comprehension. This is an active and important part of reading and you can feel it before, while or after you read anything. Through the ability to comprehend what you are reading, it will be possible for you to get the idea and understand what the writer is going to say.

Reading comprehension often includes two important parts: one is vocabulary competence and the other one is comprehension of the text or context. Vocabulary competence is being able to realize the language that is being used. But the latter one is mainly about making use of the language in order to be aware of the meaning the text is providing.

The ability to comprehend what you read is vital for a number of reasons and can offer a lot of advantages. (Sartika, F. D., Afifah, N., & Anggraini, Y., 2020). Reading productively can not only broaden your world outlook, but also develop your professional experience and thus, making your pleasure of reading better and better. Being able to comprehend a text is sure to enlarge your knowledge in many walks of life and give you a chance to gain new skills. Reading comprehension can also offer following benefits and it can help:

- to develop your productive skills by creating the chance to speak in cohesive and coherent way and write clearly;
- to be able to understand what you read and analyse it;
- to inspire you to enjoy what you read thus making your time more efficient;
- to understand the information in newspapers or journals and be aware of what is going on throughout the world and so on.

The strategies to boost reading comprehension skills

Numerous ways and strategies are available to develop your reading comprehension skills. (McNamara, D. S. (Ed.), 2007). More right and consistent practice makes you a master at what you are reading. The following strategies will come in handy to improve your reading comprehension:

Vocabulary build-up

Having a wide range of vocabulary in another language makes the language acquisition process easier and give the learners a chance enjoy themselves. (Duff,

2019). If you know the words in a text what they mean, it will be easy for you to comprehend the meaning of the text what you are reading. So to boost your range of vocabulary, you should:

- make list of the unknown or unfamiliar words and look them up in a dictionary. It will definitely help;
- read as soon as possible in order to guess what the words in a text mean to develop your ability to comprehend;
- use visuals like flashcards to learn new words which are difficult for you to memorise;
- learn new words every single day not only in books, but also in films, cartoons or journals which are your favourite. By implementing this, you can have a wide vocabulary;
- use the words that you learnt in your speech or writing to memorize them better and so on.

Making use of context clues

It would be a great idea to use the context clues in what you are reading so as to understand it better. (Oclarit, R. P., & Casinillo, L. F. , 2021).It will not be a big problem even if you have no idea about the vocabulary which are being used. Context clues are usually encountered in the sentences surrounding the words you do not know exactly. You had better pay attention to the key words or phrases in sentences and get the main idea of that sentence or the paragraph according to that information in order to make use of the context clues.

Looking for the gist

In the first place, let us look at what the gist is. The gist is the main idea or general meaning of a piece of writing, a book, speech or a conversation. While we are looking at a written text to get its main idea or find out what the writer is trying to convey, it is the case that we are reading for a gist. And it is sometimes known as skimming.

Knowing the gist or main idea of what you are reading can really help you to realize the significance an article or a book. (Sinuraya, R. A., Situmorang, P., Sihombing, R. P., Gultom, R. J., & Rambe, K. R. , 2021). Comprehending the reason why you are reading the article or the book can give you a chance to understand what the author is trying to convey or provide. While reading, it is advisable to pause every paragraph and check whether you can get the gist of what you have just read. Then, you had better strive to convey the main idea with words of your own to understand it much better.

Noting down a summary

Another useful way to develop your understanding what you read is to write a summary about what you read. Summing up asks you to determine what is significant

in the text or material that you are engaged in and convey it with your own words. (Duke, N. K., & Pearson, P. D., 2009). Writing a summary enables you to identify whether you comprehend the material that you are reading totally and memorize it for a long period of time.

Thus, noting down a summary not only makes your reading comprehension better, but also improves your writing skills.

Splitting the reading up into smaller parts

While reading a lengthy novel or an article, it is advisable to split it up into smaller parts like paragraphs or chapters, which is much more effective and useful than just read the whole book at once. (Zsigmond, 2015). After you reach the end of a section, paragraph or a chapter, do not rush to read the next page or chapter. Instead, take a few minutes to let everything soak into your mind and think about what you have just read and understood before getting back to reading. Separating what you read can help you avoid getting bored and allows you to better comprehend the information provided in the reading material that you are reading.

Limiting distractions while reading

Reading comprehension is usually about attention and if you have so many distractions, it will be hard for you to understand completely what you read. To overcome this problem, try to find a place which is bright and peaceful enough. Turn off or mute your any electronic devices such as mobile phones or laptops and so on, make sure that just you and what you are going to read.

In addition to this, try to eliminate any situation like being too tired, hungry or sleepy before starting to read because such kind of situations may cause you get distracted from what you read. Or if you are trying to read in a public place or somewhere noisy, you had better put on a pair of noise-cancelling headphones and a place away from others to avoid the noise that distracts you.

Developing a daily reading habit

Reading is an effective way for both professional and personal development. It can help you enlarge your knowledge, broaden your world outlook and make your communication skills better. But it is the case if you have a good reading habit. So what is a reading habit? How do we define it? Should we make it a daily habit for us? Yes, we definitely should as it plays a significant part in the process of improving our reading comprehension in a way that cannot be compared with any strategy above mentioned. (Leppänen, U., Aunola, K., & Nurmi, J. E. , 2005). Daily reading means that you read something interesting or favorite for yourself for some time in order to learn something. However, making a daily reading a habit can be hard, but it is worth developing it. So in order to develop a daily reading habit, you should:

- set some time to read and stick to that schedule to turn it into a daily reading habit;
- find and choose books or something you find fascinating to read;
- set a reading aim for yourself, for example, reading a book or a story for a certain period of time a day, or a number of pages of a book, which comes in handy, too;
- not forget that daily reading is your daily routine and carry on reinforcing it,

Reading per day improves not only your level of knowledge, but also your concentration, lexical resource and overall perspective.

Conclusion

Taking everything into consideration, reading comprehension skills play a significant role during the process of language acquisition, in particular, foreign languages like English. By using the strategies provided above, you can develop your ability to read and comprehend what you read. In addition to improving your reading comprehension skills, these strategies help you develop your productive skills like such as being able communicate well orally and write in a clear, coherent and cohesive way if you implement the strategies well by sticking to a certain schedule. Reading comprehension is something that serves a base for overall improvement.

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